

An Algorithm for the Map Labeling Problem with Two Kinds of Priorities

Authors : Noboru Abe, Yoshinori Amai, Toshinori Nakatake, Sumio Masuda, Kazuaki Yamaguchi

Abstract : We consider the problem of placing labels of the points on a plane. For each point, its position, the size of its label and a priority are given. Moreover, several candidates of its label positions are prespecified, and each of such label positions is assigned a priority. The objective of our problem is to maximize the total sum of priorities of placed labels and their points. By refining a labeling algorithm that can use these priorities, we propose a new heuristic algorithm which is more suitable for treating the assigned priorities.

Keywords : map labeling, greedy algorithm, heuristic algorithm, priority

Conference Title : ICCSIE 2014 : International Conference on Computer Science and Information Engineering

Conference Location : Tokyo, Japan

Conference Dates : May 29-30, 2014